

1 **APPROXIMATION BY SZÁSZ-MIRAKYAN OPERATORS USING**
2 **DUNKL-APPELL POLYNOMIALS OF CLASS $A^{(2)}$**

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we present a modified form of the Szász-Mirakyan operators constructed using of Dunkl-Appell polynomials of class $A^{(2)}$. Our aim is to explore the approximation behavior of this new class of operators by employing tools such as the classical modulus of continuity and the Lipschitz class.

5 1. INTRODUCTION

6 In recent years, approximation theory has become a focus of extensive mathemat-
7 ical research. Many studies examine linear positive operators built from generating
8 functions of special function classes, and they report numerous important results
9 in approximation theory [1, 4, 9, 12, 13, 15]. Notably, Jakimovski and Leviatan
10 introduced a generalized operator $P_m(\psi; \xi)$ using Appell polynomials in their work
11 [7].

$$(1) \quad P_m(\psi; \xi) = \frac{e^{-m\xi}}{g(1)} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} r_j(m\xi) \psi\left(\frac{j}{m}\right), \quad m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

12 Furthermore, Sucu [11] defined the Dunkl analogue of Szász operators with the help
13 of a generalization of the exponential function given by Rosenblum [10] as follows

$$(2) \quad S_m^\mu(\psi; \xi) = \frac{1}{e_\mu(m\xi)} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(m\xi)^j}{\gamma_\mu(j)} \psi\left(\frac{j + 2\mu\theta_j}{m}\right), \quad \xi \geq 0, m \in \mathbb{N},$$

14 under the assumption $\psi \in C[0, \infty)$. The Dunkl-type exponential function $e_\mu(\xi)$
15 given by Rosenblum [10] is defined by

$$(3) \quad e_\mu(\xi) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{\xi^j}{\gamma_\mu(j)},$$

16 where the coefficients $\gamma_\mu(j)$ are given by

$$(4) \quad \gamma_\mu(2j) = \frac{2^{2j} j!}{\Gamma(j + \mu + \frac{1}{2})} \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_\mu(2j + 1) = \frac{2^{2j+1} j! \Gamma(j + \mu + \frac{3}{2})}{\Gamma(\mu + \frac{1}{2})},$$

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1 for $j \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $\mu \geq -1/2$ and Γ denotes the Euler gamma function. These coefficients
 2 satisfy the recurrence relation [10]

$$(5) \quad \gamma_\mu(j) = (j + 2\mu\theta_j)\gamma_\mu(j - 1), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots$$

3 For $p \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $\theta_\mu(j)$ is defined as

$$(6) \quad \theta_j = \frac{1 + (-1)^{j-1}}{2} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j = 2v \\ 1 & \text{if } j = 2v + 1. \end{cases}$$

4 Let us recall the Dunkl derivative operator [5, 6] for $\mu \geq -1/2$ as

$$(7) \quad D_{\mu,\xi}(\psi(\xi)) = \psi'(\xi) + \frac{\mu}{\xi}(\psi(\xi) - \psi(-\xi)),$$

5 where $\psi(\xi)$ is an entire function. Also it is clear that D_μ reduces to the classical
 6 derivative when $\mu = 0$. Let us apply Dunkl derivative operator [5, 10] on some
 7 functions

$$(8) \quad D_{\mu,\xi}(e_\mu(\xi\tau)) = \tau e_\mu(\xi\tau)$$

8 and

$$(9) \quad D_{\mu,\xi}(\xi^m) = \frac{\gamma_\mu(m)}{\gamma_\mu(m-1)}\xi^{m-1}.$$

9 Cheikh and Gained have defined Dunkl-Appell polynomials in [3]. Dunkl-Appell
 10 polynomials are symbolized by $p_{j,\mu}(\xi)$ and defined by

$$(10) \quad p_{j,\mu}(\xi) = \sum_{m=0}^j \binom{j}{m}_\mu c_{j-m}\xi^m, \quad c_0 \neq 0,$$

11 where $\binom{j}{m}_\mu$ denotes the Dunkl-binomial coefficient and is defined as follows

$$(11) \quad \binom{j}{m}_\mu = \frac{\gamma_\mu(m)}{\gamma_\mu(j)\gamma_\mu(m-j)}.$$

12 Moreover, the Appell polynomials $p_{j,\mu}(\xi)$ have the generating functions of the form
 13 [3]

$$(12) \quad S(\tau)e_\mu(\xi\tau) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{p_{j,\mu}(\xi)}{\gamma_\mu(j)}\tau^j,$$

14 where S is an analytic function and is defined by

$$(13) \quad S(\tau) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} c_j \frac{\tau^j}{\gamma_\mu(j)}.$$

15 Kazmin [8] introduced the Appell polynomials $p_j(\xi)$ of class $A^{(2)}$ which are defined
 16 by the generating function

$$(14) \quad U(\tau)e^{\xi\tau} + V(\tau)e^{-\xi\tau} = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_j(\xi)\tau^j,$$

1 where

$$(15) \quad U(\tau) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_j}{j!} \tau^j \quad \text{and} \quad V(\tau) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_j}{j!} \tau^j,$$

2 are power series. Varma [14] has defined the corresponding operator by using Appell
3 polynomials of class $A^{(2)}$

$$(16) \quad T_m(\psi; \xi) = \frac{1}{U(\tau)e^{\xi\tau} + V(\tau)e^{-\xi\tau}} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_j(m\xi) \psi\left(\frac{j}{m}\right),$$

4 with the restrictions $U(1) > 0, V(1) \geq 0$ and $p_j(\xi) > 0$ for all $j = 0, 1, \dots$. Now, we
5 define Dunkl analogue of Appell polynomials of class $A^{(2)}$

$$(17) \quad z_{j,\mu}(\xi) = \sum_{m=0}^j \binom{j}{m}_{\mu} a_{j-m} \xi^m + \binom{j}{m}_{\mu} b_{j-m} \xi^m, \quad c_0 \neq 0.$$

6 Furthermore, $z_{j,\mu}(\xi)$ have the generating functions of the form

$$(18) \quad U(\tau)e_{\mu}(\xi\tau) + V(\tau)e_{\mu}(-\xi\tau) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z_{j,\mu}(\xi)}{\gamma_{\mu}(j)} \tau^j,$$

7 where

$$(19) \quad U(\tau) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_j}{\gamma_{\mu}(j)} \tau^j \quad \text{and} \quad V(\tau) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_j}{\gamma_{\mu}(j)} \tau^j.$$

8 The paper is organized as follows. Firstly, we present the construction of the
9 modified Szász–Mirakyan operators based on Dunkl–Appell polynomials of class
10 $A^{(2)}$ and describe their fundamental properties. In Section 3, we investigate the
11 convergence behavior of these operators via the modulus of continuity and the
12 Lipschitz class. Finally, we present the conclusion, summarizing the main results
13 in Section 4.

14 2. CONSTRUCTION AND BASIC PROPERTIES OF THE OPERATOR $R_m(\psi; \xi)$

15 In this section, we give some lemmas and theorems. Let us first define the
16 operator $R_m(\psi; \xi)$,

$$(20) \quad R_m(\psi; \xi) = \frac{1}{U(1)e_{\mu}(m\xi) + V(1)e_{\mu}(-m\xi)} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z_{j,\mu}(m\xi)}{\gamma_{\mu}(j)} \psi\left(\frac{j + 2\mu\theta_j}{m}\right),$$

17 where $\xi \geq 0, m \in \mathbb{N}$ and μ is a real parameter with $|\mu| < 1/2$ and $\psi \in C[0, \infty)$. $U(\tau)$
18 and $V(\tau)$ are analytic functions given in Eq. (19) where $U(1) \neq 0$ and $V(1) \neq 0$.

1 **Lemma 2.1.** *For the generating function given in Eq. (18), the following equalities*

$$\begin{aligned}
 (i) \quad & \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z_{j,\mu}(m\xi)}{\gamma_{\mu}(j)} = U(1)e_{\mu}(m\xi) + V(1)e_{\mu}(-m\xi), \\
 (ii) \quad & \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z_{j+1,\mu}(m\xi)}{\gamma_{\mu}(j)} = e_{\mu}(m\xi) \left(m\xi U(1) + (U)'(1) + \mu(V(1) - V(-1)) \right) \\
 & + e_{\mu}(-m\xi) \left(-m\xi V(1) + (V)'(1) + \mu(U(1) - U(-1)) \right), \\
 (iii) \quad & \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z_{j+1,\mu}(m\xi)}{\gamma_{\mu}(j)} (-1)^j = e_{\mu}(-m\xi) \left(m\xi U(-1) + (U)'(-1) + \mu(V(1) - V(-1)) \right) \\
 & + e_{\mu}(m\xi) \left(m\xi V(-1) + (V)'(-1) + \mu(U(1) - U(-1)) \right), \\
 (iv) \quad & \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z_{j+2,\mu}(m\xi)}{\gamma_{\mu}(j)} = e_{\mu}(m\xi) \left(m^2 \xi^2 U(1) + 2m\xi (U)'(1) + (U)''(1) + 2\mu(V)'(1) - \mu(V(1) - V(-1)) \right) \\
 & + e_{\mu}(-m\xi) \left(2\mu(U)'(1) - \mu(U(1) - U(-1)) + m^2 \xi^2 V(1) + (V)''(1) \right) - 2m\xi (V)'(1)
 \end{aligned}$$

2 *are satisfied.*

3 *Proof.* (i) If we take $\tau = 1$ and $m\xi$ instead of ξ in Eq. (18), then we obtain the proof.

4

5 (ii) Let us apply the operator $D_{\mu,\xi}$ on both sides of the equality (18) and use
6 the equalities (3), (4) and (5). Furthermore, by taking $\tau = 1$ and $m\xi$ instead of ξ
7 in Eq. (18), we get the second proof.

8

9 For the proof of (iii) and (iv) equalities, the same steps are applied and get the
10 desired result. \square

11 **Lemma 2.2.** *For the operators $R_m(\psi; \xi)$, we have*

$$\begin{aligned}
 (i) \quad & R_m(1; \xi) = 1, \\
 (ii) \quad & R_m(s; \xi) = \xi \frac{U(1)e_{\mu}(m\xi) - V(1)e_{\mu}(-m\xi)}{U(1)e_{\mu}(m\xi) + V(1)e_{\mu}(-m\xi)} + \frac{(U)'(1) + \mu(V(1) - V(-1))}{m} \omega_1(\xi), \\
 (iii) \quad & R_m(s^2; \xi) = \xi^2 + \frac{\xi}{m} \left((2(U)'(1) + U(1) + V(-1)) \omega_1(\xi) \right. \\
 & + (-2(V)'(1) - V(1) + V(-1)) \omega_2(\xi) \left. \right) + ((U)''(1) + 2\mu(V)'(1) - \mu(V(1) - V(-1))) \omega_1(\xi) \\
 & + ((V)''(1) + 2\mu(U)'(1) - \mu(U(1) - U(-1))) \omega_2(\xi) + ((U)'(1) \\
 & + \mu(V(1) - V(-1)) + (V)'(-1) + \mu(U(1) - U(-1))) \omega_1(\xi) \\
 & + ((V)'(1) + \mu(U(1) - U(-1)) + (U)'(-1) + \\
 & \mu(V(1) - V(-1))) \omega_2(\xi),
 \end{aligned}$$

12 where $\omega_1(\xi) = \frac{e_{\mu}(m\xi)}{U(1)e_{\mu}(m\xi) + V(1)e_{\mu}(-m\xi)}$ and $\omega_2(\xi) = \frac{e_{\mu}(-m\xi)}{U(1)e_{\mu}(m\xi) + V(1)e_{\mu}(-m\xi)}$.

13 *Proof.* (i) We obtain the proof of the first equality by using definition of operator
14 and Lemma 2.1.

- 1 (ii) For the proof of the second equality, it is enough to use recursion relation in
2 Eq. (5) to get

$$R_m(s; \xi) = \frac{1}{m(U(1)e_\mu(m\xi) + V(1)e_\mu(-m\xi))} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z_{j,\mu}(m\xi)}{\gamma_\mu(j-1)}.$$

- 3 Moreover, if we replace j by $j+1$ and use Lemma 2.1, then we arrived at the desired
4 result.
5 (iii) Here, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} R_m(s^2; \xi) &= \frac{1}{U(1)e_\mu(m\xi) + V(1)e_\mu(-m\xi)} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z_{j,\mu}(m\xi)}{\gamma_\mu(j)} \left(\frac{j + 2\mu\theta_j}{m} \right)^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{m^2(U(1)e_\mu(m\xi) + V(1)e_\mu(-m\xi))} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{z_{j+1,\mu}(m\xi)}{\gamma_\mu(j)} \left(j + 1 + 2\mu\theta_{j+1} \right)^2, \end{aligned}$$

- 6
7 where $\theta_{j+1} = (-1)^j + \theta_j$. This completes the proof of the Lemma 2.2. \square

8 **Lemma 2.3.** *The central moments of $R_m(\psi; \xi)$ are given*

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & R_m(1; \xi) = 1, \\ (ii) \quad & R_m((s - \xi); \xi) = \xi \frac{U(1)e_\mu(m\xi) - V(1)e_\mu(-m\xi)}{U(1)e_\mu(m\xi) + V(1)e_\mu(-m\xi)} + \frac{(U)'(1) + \mu(V(1) - V(-1))}{m} \omega_1(\xi) \\ & + \frac{(V)'(1) + \mu(U(1) - U(-1))}{m} \omega_2(\xi) - \xi, \\ (iii) \quad & R_m((s - \xi)^2; \xi) = \xi^2 + \frac{\xi}{m} \left((2(U)'(1) + U(1) + V(-1))\omega_1(\xi) + (-2(V)'(1) - V(1) \right. \\ & + V(-1))\omega_2(\xi) \left. \right) + \left((U)''(1) + 2\mu(V)'(1) - \mu(V(1) - V(-1)) \right) \omega_1(\xi) + \left((V)''(1) + 2\mu(U)'(1) \right. \\ & - \mu(U(1) - U(-1)) \left. \right) \omega_2(\xi) + \left((U)'(1) + \mu(V(1) - V(-1)) + (V)'(-1) + \mu(U(1) - U(-1)) \right) \omega_1(\xi) \\ & + \left((V)'(1) + \mu(U(1) - U(-1)) + (U)'(-1) + \mu(V(1) - V(-1)) \right) \omega_2(\xi) \\ & - 2x \left(\xi \frac{U(1)e_\mu(m\xi) - V(1)e_\mu(-m\xi)}{U(1)e_\mu(m\xi) + V(1)e_\mu(-m\xi)} + \frac{(U)'(1) + \mu(V(1) - V(-1))}{m} \omega_1(\xi) \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{(V)'(1) + \mu(U(1) - U(-1))}{m} \omega_2(\xi) \right) - \xi^2. \end{aligned}$$

9 *Proof.* (i) The proof of the first equality is clear from the definition of operator R_m
10 and Lemma 2.1.

11 (ii) From the linearity of the operator R_m , it is obvious that

$$R_m((s - \xi); \xi) = R_m(s; \xi) - \xi,$$

12 using by Lemma 2.1, we obtain the desired result.

13 (iii) The same steps are applied to get the proof of last equality. \square

14 **Theorem 2.1.** *For every $\psi \in E = \{\psi \text{ is continuous on } [0, \infty), \frac{\psi(\xi)}{1+\xi^2} \text{ is convergent as } \xi \rightarrow$*
15 *$\infty\}$, we have*

$$(21) \quad \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} R_m(\psi; \xi) = \psi(\xi),$$

16 *on each compact subset of $[0, \infty)$.*

1 *Proof.* Using well-known Korovkin Theorem [2] for the proof, we get the desired
2 result. \square

3 CONVERGENCE PROPERTIES OF THE OPERATOR $R_m(\psi; \xi)$

4 In what follows, we get some convergence results for the operator $R_m(\psi; \xi)$.
5 Firstly, let us recall some definitions.

6
7 **Definition 3.1.** $\tilde{C}[0, \infty)$ is the space of uniformly continuous functions on $[0, \infty)$.
8 The modulus of continuity of $\psi \in \tilde{C}[0, \infty)$, denoted by

$$(22) \quad \omega(\psi; \delta) = \sup_{|\zeta| \leq \delta} \left\{ |\psi(\xi + \zeta) - \psi(\xi)| : \xi \in [0, \infty) \right\}.$$

10 Furthermore, $C_B[0, \infty)$ is the space of continuous and bounded functions on $[0, \infty)$.
11 Then, the following equality with the norm holds

$$(23) \quad \|\psi\|_{C_B^2[0, \infty)} = \|\psi\|_{C_B[0, \infty)} + \|\psi'\|_{C_B[0, \infty)} + \|\psi''\|_{C_B[0, \infty)},$$

13 where for all $\psi \in C_B^2[0, \infty)$,

$$(24) \quad C_B^2[0, \infty) = \{\psi \in C_B[0, \infty) : \psi', \psi'' \in C_B[0, \infty)\}.$$

15 **Definition 3.2.** $Lip_M(\alpha)$ is the Lipschitz class of order α on $[0, \infty)$. If $\psi \in$
16 $Lip_M(\alpha)$, then the following inequality is satisfied

$$(25) \quad |\psi(\xi) - \psi(\zeta)| \leq M|\xi - \zeta|^\alpha,$$

18 where $\xi, \zeta \in [0, \infty)$, $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ and $M > 0$.

20 **Lemma 3.1.** We give the following inequality for $\psi \in C_B^2[0, \infty)$

$$(26) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq [\Delta_1 + \Delta_2] \|\psi\|_{C_B^2[0, \infty)},$$

22 where $\Delta_1 = R_m((s - \xi); \xi)$ and $\Delta_2 = R_m((s - \xi)^2; \xi)$ are central moments given in
24 Lemma 2.3.

25 *Proof.* For the proof of the lemma, we use Taylor series of the function ψ

$$(27) \quad \psi(s) = \psi(\xi) + (s - \xi)\psi'(\xi) + \frac{(s - \xi)^2}{2!}\psi''(\sigma), \sigma \in (\xi, s).$$

26 If we apply the R_m to both sides of inequality (27) and use linearity of the operator,
27 we get

$$(28) \quad R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi) = \psi'(\xi)\Delta_1 + \frac{\psi''(\sigma)}{2}\Delta_2.$$

$$(29) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq \Delta_1 \|\psi'\| + \Delta_2 \|\psi''\|,$$

1 from which, we can give the following inequality

2

$$(30) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq [\Delta_1 + \Delta_2] \|\psi\|_{C_B^2[0, \infty)}.$$

3

□

4 **Theorem 3.1.** *If $\psi \in Lip_M(\alpha)$, we have*

$$(31) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq M(\Delta_2)^{\alpha/2},$$

5 where $\Delta_2 = R_m((s - \xi)^2; \xi)$.

6 *Proof.* Since $\psi \in Lip_M(\alpha)$, we have the following inequality

$$(32) \quad |\psi(s) - \psi(\xi)| \leq M|s - \xi|^\alpha.$$

7 Applying the operator R_m to both sides of the inequality, and using the linearity
8 of the operator, we obtain

$$(33) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq MR_m(|s - \xi|^\alpha; \xi).$$

9 By applying Hölder's inequality and using Lemma 2.3, we get

$$(34) \quad R_m(|s - \xi|^\alpha; \xi) \leq (R_m(|s - \xi|^2; \xi))^{\alpha/2} = (\Delta_2)^{\alpha/2},$$

10 from which, it follows

$$(35) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq M(\Delta_2)^{\alpha/2}.$$

11

□

12 **Theorem 3.2.** *The operators $R_m(\psi; \xi)$ verify the inequality*

$$(36) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq 2\omega(\psi; \delta),$$

13 where $\psi \in \tilde{C}[0, \infty)$.

14 *Proof.* From the definition of the modulus of continuity and linearity of operator,
15 we give the following inequality

$$(37) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq R_m(|\psi(\tau) - \psi(\xi)|; \xi) \leq \omega(\psi; \delta) \left(\frac{R_m(|\tau - \xi|; \xi)}{\delta} + 1 \right).$$

16 From the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality for sum, we get

$$(38) \quad R_m(|\tau - \xi|; \xi) \leq \sqrt{\Delta_2},$$

17 and using the above inequalities we have

$$(39) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq \omega(\psi; \delta) \left(\frac{\sqrt{\Delta_2}}{\delta} + 1 \right).$$

18 Here, we choose $\delta = \sqrt{\Delta_2}$ and we get

$$(40) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq 2\omega(\psi; \delta),$$

19 which ends the proof. □

20 **Theorem 3.3.** *The following inequality is hold for the operator $R_m(\psi; \xi)$*

21

$$(41) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq 2M \{ \min(1, \delta_m(\xi)) \|\psi\|_{C_B[0, \infty)} + \omega_2(\psi, \sqrt{\delta_m(\xi)}) \}$$

22

23 where $\psi \in C_B[0, \infty)$, $\delta_m = \sqrt{\Delta_2} + \frac{\Delta_2}{2}$ and M is the positive constant.

1 *Proof.* Since $\psi \in C_B^2[0, \infty)$, we give

$$(42) \quad \psi(\tau) - \psi(\xi) = \psi'(\xi)(\tau - \xi) + \psi''(c)\frac{(\tau - \xi)^2}{2}$$

2 where $\xi < c < \tau$. Let us use linearity of operators $R_m(\psi; \xi)$ and apply operator
3 both sides of Eq. (42) and we get

$$(43) \quad R_m(\psi(\tau); \xi) - \psi(\xi) = \psi' R_m(\tau - \xi; \xi) + \psi''(c)R_m\left(\frac{(\tau - \xi)^2}{2}; \xi\right)$$

4

$$(44) \quad |R_m(\psi(\tau); \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq |\psi'(\xi)|R_m(|\tau - \xi|; \xi) + \frac{|\psi''(c)|}{2}R_m((\tau - \xi)^2; \xi)$$

5 By using Lemma 2.3, we can write

$$(45) \quad |R_m(\psi(\tau); \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq |\psi'| \sqrt{\Delta_2} + \frac{|\psi''(c)|}{2} \Delta_2$$

6

$$(46) \quad \leq \left(\sqrt{\Delta_2} + \frac{\Delta_2}{2}\right)(\|\psi'\|_{C_B[0, \infty)} + \|\psi''\|_{C_B[0, \infty)})$$

7

$$(47) \quad \leq \left(\sqrt{\Delta_2} + \frac{\Delta_2}{2}\right)\|\psi\|_{C_B^2[0, \infty)}$$

8 From the above inequality, we acquire

$$(48) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| = |R_m(\psi; \xi) - R_m(\phi; \xi) + R_m(\phi; \xi) - \phi(\xi) + \phi(\xi) - \psi(\xi)|$$

9

$$(49) \quad \leq R_m(|\psi - \phi|; \xi) + |\psi(\xi) - \phi(\xi)| + |R_m(\phi; \xi) - \phi(\xi)|$$

10

$$(50) \quad \leq 2\|\psi - \phi\|_{C_B[0, \infty)} + 2\|\phi\|_{C_B^2[0, \infty)}\left(\sqrt{\Delta_2} + \frac{\Delta_2}{2}\right)$$

11 Now, we recall that the second modulus countinuity of $\psi \in C_B^2[0, \infty)$ is given as

$$(51) \quad \omega_2(\psi; \delta) = \sup_{0 < s \leq \delta} \{|\psi(\xi + 2s) - 2\psi(\xi + s) + \psi(\xi)|\}$$

12 where $\delta > 0$ and $\xi \in [0, \infty)$. The relation between Peetre's K -functional of the
13 function $\psi \in C_B[0, \infty)$ and ω_2 is as follows

$$(52) \quad K(\psi; \delta) \leq M\{\omega_2(\psi; \sqrt{\delta}) + \min(1, \delta)\|\psi\|_{C_B[0, \infty)}\}$$

14 for all $\delta > 0$. Here, M is the a positive constant. From (52), we have

$$(53) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq 2K(\psi; \left(\sqrt{\Delta_2} + \frac{\Delta_2}{2}\right))$$

15 by taking infimum both sides of (50) for $\phi \in C_B^2[0, \infty)$ and using (53), we get

$$(54) \quad |R_m(\psi; \xi) - \psi(\xi)| \leq 2M\{\omega_2(\psi; \sqrt{\delta_m(x)}) + \min(1, \delta_m)\|\psi\|\}$$

16 where $\delta_m = \sqrt{\Delta_2} + \frac{\Delta_2}{2}$. □

4. CONCLUSION

1

2 In this paper, we have constructed and analyzed a new class of Szász–Mirakyan
3 operators generated by Dunkl-Appell polynomials of class $A^{(2)}$. The rate of con-
4 vergence estimates were obtained via the classical modulus of continuity and the
5 Lipschitz class. Moreover, using the Korovkin-type theorem, we established the
6 convergence of the proposed operators on compact subsets of $[0, \infty)$. These re-
7 sults extend previous studies on Dunkl-type approximation operators and highlight
8 the role of Dunkl-Appell polynomials of class $A^{(2)}$ in producing more general and
9 flexible approximation processes. Future research may explore applications of the
10 present operators as well as potential extensions to multivariate settings. We believe
11 that the proposed approach provides a useful foundation for further developments
12 in approximation theory within the framework of Dunkl analysis.

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